

Complexity and Polycentricity: Empirical Evidence from the Seshat Global

History Databank

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This document complements a book chapter titled “*The Problem of Complexity and the Emergence of Polycentric Political Order*” (Daems and Schaefer, In Press), in which we discuss the emergence of polycentric political systems through the lens of historical social complexity formation. In the chapter, we illustrate our theoretical model through a comparison of the governance structures in Han China and ancient Rome. Here, we provide further empirical validation of our proposal through a more extensive historical analysis using data from the Seshat Global History Databank.¹

The proposition under consideration is that, at least beyond a certain point, increasing social complexity is incompatible with effective centralized control. Empirically, this means that there should exist a strong correlation between growing social complexity and the emergence of polycentricity. Although we have carefully explained the meanings of these terms, defining empirical indicators for such abstract notions is itself a difficult task. In defining such indicators, one faces two competing desiderata. First, there is the conceptual question of precision: does the empirical indicator truly measure the relevant concept?

Second, there is the practical question of data acquisition: can we collect data on the empirical indicator

¹ The Seshat data set is available online: [Seshat: Global History Databank](#). Analysis is based on the Equinox 2020 release of the dataset (Turchin et al. 2022).

from a sufficiently large sample to do a proper hypothesis test? Although for some societies we possess reliable and detailed information about social and governmental structures, to collect a sufficiently large sample from a wide array of societies we must rely upon rough proxies, rather than the richer notions of complexity and polycentricity explained above. This is necessary since, in order to scientifically test propositions, that is, in order to determine whether these propositions are likely to generalize to societies other than those we study, it is imperative to consider a large sample of different historical societies. We thus face a trade-off between *precision* and *generality*.²

In order to adequately address this trade-off, we supplement our initial case study of Han China and Rome with a broader empirical analysis. Here, we draw on the Seshat data set, which provides data from 414 societies across 30 regions on social complexity trajectories over the last 6000 years. The dataset contains almost 200 variables covering aspects of social complexity, warfare, agricultural production, institutional structures, economy and technology. Analysis of the dataset indicates that the social complexity variables can be grouped in 9 strongly interrelated clusters: polity population, polity size, capital population, hierarchical complexity, government, infrastructure, information systems, specialized texts and monetary systems (Turchin et al. 2018). These variables were selected to represent different aspects of social complexity, but, as we will see, several of them work as proxies for what we have called polycentricity. This large sample allows us to employ cross-cultural quantitative comparisons to test our central hypothesis, viz. that political polycentricity supports economic and social complexity.

The first step is to identify suitable empirical indicators for social complexity and polycentricity. Social complexity refers to large numbers of adaptive, diverse, and interdependent individuals. The crucial point about such systems is that they must generate, store, and transmit large amounts of information. Several empirical measures have been proposed and a rich body of literature exists on

² Our term *precision* encompasses both construct validity (Ghiselli, Campbell, and Zedeck 1981) and criterion-related validity (Nunnally 1978, 87), while *generality* refers to external validity (Campbell 1957).

approximating and measuring social complexity. For the most part, however, it has remained an elusive concept, and constructing an encompassing and useful measure of complexity has proven to be extremely difficult (Page 2011, 27). Some examples of rough measures include the population of the largest settlement (Bowden 1972; Chick 1997) or the area of controlled territory (Turchin et. al. 2013). These austere measurements roughly capture the idea of large numbers of interdependent individuals. They also correlate with other proposed measurements of complexity, including richer composite measurements (Chick 1997, 300). Most importantly, societies comprising large settlements and extensive territories face elevated informational demands, i.e. the *complexity problem*. A preliminary statistical analysis, therefore, can justifiably rely on these two measures — population of the largest settlement and total area of controlled territory — as rough approximations of social complexity.

Polycentricity, on the other hand, has not received as much attention from statistically-minded cultural researchers. The concept has been analyzed rigorously in various places, but case studies are a far more common methodology than statistical analysis (Thiel et. al. 2019). Our own construal of polycentricity — relying on Aligica and Tarko (2012, 257) as well as Stephan, Marshall, and McGinnis (2019) — highlighted the processes of vertical and horizontal competition between multiple levels of decision-making power. It is the presence of *multiple scales* of governance, as well as *diversity* within each scale, that supports the beneficial flow of information that we have identified as the key advantage of polycentric political order. Thanks to the Seshat data set, we have access to two relevant proxies, one that records the number of scales present in the set of decision-making entities (Figs. 1-2), another which records the diversity of decision-making types. The latter, which we label “professions” (Fig. 3), tracks the number of distinct government agent types. Examples of government agent types include judges, bureaucrats, military officers, and priests. This variable is intended to work as a proxy for competition within and between levels. For instance, religious officials offers governance services including “public goods provision, flexible local governance, and neutral arbitration of rules” (Gill 2021,

313). These services can be viewed as a potential substitute for services provided by the military or bureaucrat officials. Different government agents also operate at different scales, allowing this proxy to track the potential for vertical competition as well as horizontal competition.

These proxies are far from perfect. The main objection is that a sophisticated autocratic state could manifest multiple levels of hierarchy. If there is no upward influence through the hierarchy and if there is limited horizontal interdependence within each level, then the governance structure will be far from polycentric. Moreover, the presence of multiple scales and within-scale diversity does not imply a process of competition between decision-making jurisdictions. If individuals are prohibited from migrating to different jurisdictions and if the roles assigned to each level in the administrative hierarchy are inflexible, then there will be no competition and the structure will not be polycentric as we have conceptualized it.

Although multiple decision-making levels and within-level diversity are not *sufficient* for polycentric structures, they are, nevertheless, *necessary*. We can thus define a legitimate, although preliminary, scientific test of our hypothesis on the basis of the indicators we have laid out. Our hypothesis predicts a greater number of decision-making levels and more diversity within those levels insofar as social complexity increases. If we do not observe this outcome, then our hypothesis has been falsified. The ensuing analysis can thus be viewed as a first preliminary test of our hypothesis.

Figure 1: Comparison of territorial extent (in square kilometers on logarithmic scale) of polities ranked per administrative level

Figure 2: Comparison of territorial extent (in square kilometers on logarithmic scale) of polities ranked per settlement level

While we can immediately note a fairly large degree of variation, figures 1 and 2 show that our first indicator for complexity (polity territory size, displayed in kilometers squared on a logarithmic scale) does, indeed, correlate with our first indicator for polycentricity (hierarchical levels). These charts show the same overall trend when we measure hierarchical levels in terms of settlement hierarchy. Interestingly, territory sizes appear to flatten off and reach a plateau from administrative level 7 onwards. This could suggest an upper limit for the addition of extra levels in the administrative hierarchy that can viably support increasing polity sizes. For the settlement hierarchy levels, this plateau appears less pronounced. Instead, we see in this graph an 'intermediate' plateau of roughly comparable polity sizes for levels 3 to 5, suggesting a threshold between small and large polities. This would indicate that the addition of several levels of settlement hierarchy is needed before the polity reaches the required 'critical mass' to make this transition.

Territorial size provides only one proxy for complexity. A comparison of the same indicators for polycentricity with overall polity population numbers recorded in the Seshat dataset provided largely comparable trends, thus corroborating the observations in figures 1 and 2.

While the number of hierarchical levels highlight one aspect of polycentricity, they do not capture the crucial feature of competition within and between levels. For that, we turn to the diversity of governance providers. Here, we start to approach the limits of historical data as such diversity is notoriously difficult to capture in data points for cross-cultural analysis. The Seshat dataset attempts to deal with the conundrum of overall societal diversity by covering several variables related to diversity in specific domains such as government administrators, religious officials, economic professions, and social status. From those variables, we will look at one in particular: the presence or absence of specialized governance-providing professions such as military and religious 'professionals' (e.g. professional soldiers and priests).

Figure 3: Presence and absence of professionals in non-governmental organizations for polities ranked by territorial extent (in square kilometers on logarithmic scale).

In figure 3, we inspect the presence of professionals in non-governmental organizations — here the military and priesthood — against the overall polity population. We observe large degree of overlap between absence and presence of these classes, as is the clear concentration of professional diversity at the higher end of the spectrum of population sizes. It is nevertheless remarkable that the concentration of profession diversity is far greater at the high-complexity end of the spectrum. This suggests that profession diversity is not a necessary factor for increasing social complexity, but can be proposed as a useful indicator of complexity when present. It might be interesting to explore this point in more chronological detail in the future and assess whether the development of profession diversity should be considered a crucial factor, not for the *emergence* of social complexity, but for its *continuation and maintenance*.

The figures shown above indicate some correlations between our selected proxies for social complexity (territory size and population numbers) and polycentricity (hierarchical levels of settlement and administration, and profession diversity), even though we cannot yet draw any straightforward

conclusions at this stage. Figures 1 and 2 clearly illustrate a general trend where, to a certain extent, additional layers of hierarchy need to be developed to allow larger polities to develop. Once we move on to incorporate professional diversity as an indicator for how these hierarchies might have been established in different domains (political, military and religious), the picture becomes markedly murkier and large degrees of overlap are observed.

On the one hand, this preliminary analysis appears to corroborate our general premise that polycentricity and the associated multiple levels of decision-making are a necessary (but not sufficient) factor for the continued development and maintenance of social complexity. On the other hand, the ways in which these multiple levels were shaped through within-level diversity need to be clarified in order to gain a proper understanding of *how* polycentric systems enable increases in social complexity.

To do so, we need to draw on more detailed information regarding the underlying structure of the decision-making levels and the nature of the connections between different levels. This detailed comparison has been undertaken elsewhere (Daems and Schaefer, In Press). To conclude this part of the analysis, however, we can point toward one final element drawn from the Seshat dataset, pertaining to the correlation between overall polity size with the *degree of centralization* of the polity in figure 4. This variable identifies the relationships between socio-political units within a given area through five stages of polity formation: (1) a quasi-polity consisting of politically independent groups with some degree of integration on an economic or cultural level; (2) a 'nominal' configuration in which regional rulers pay nominal allegiance to an overall ruler but maintain independence on all important aspects of governing; (3) a 'loose' configuration in which the central government exercises a certain degree of control over important matters such as military arrangements and diplomacy but regional rulers maintain extensive freedom in internal affairs; (4) a confederated state characterized by formal integration of regions within a larger polity, but where regions still enjoy a large degree of autonomy in internal (regional)

government; (5) a unitary state in which regional governors are appointed and removed by the central authorities and taxes are imposed by, and transmitted to the center.

Figure 4: Comparison of territorial extent (in square kilometers on a logarithmic scale) of polities divided in five stages of polity formation.

It is clear from figure 4 that stronger intra-polity structures of regional integration allow polities to grow larger. Again, a comparison with population numbers resulted in largely similar trends. The graph clearly shows that the most complex societies are generally found in the categories of the confederate and unitary state, but with little difference between those two categories. Given that we have not yet established the underlying causal mechanisms behind this observation, we must again refrain from drawing strong conclusions. The data suggest, however, that a transition from regionalized autonomy to centralized control offers little advantage in terms of increasing territory sizes.

It is therefore tempting to suggest that these preliminary analyses point towards the necessity of polycentric structures for the emergence and development of social complexity, whereas higher degrees of centralization offer no tangible benefits to continue this process. It should of course be noted that the

Seshat data used to produce figure 4 is coded to rank polities across various stages in a process of increasing degree of centralization, implying that the unitary state would be the necessary (and unavoidable?) endpoint of this progression. This approach is too teleological, and it is important to point out this does not necessarily need to correspond with the actual historical development of the included polities. If we take our theoretical premise as an analytical starting point, we would actually expect to see the strongest increases in social complexity to occur during the stage of polycentric configurations or “confederate states.” As a corollary of that assumption, we would expect that given the additional costs (both in capital and information processing) associated with higher degrees of centralization, combined with its limited added benefits, many polities would have had comparably more trouble maintaining their social complexity in a centralized configuration.

To test these hypotheses, however, we would have to conduct extensive time series analysis of the Seshat dataset. Moreover, additional data collection would be necessary to obtain the relevant data to test the polycentricity thesis *strictu sensu* on a large scale. Both would go beyond the scope of the present paper as we restrict ourselves here to providing a first outline towards the usage of archaeological/historical data to explore the historical development of polycentricity. We can conclude here that large-scale data compilation from historical societies offers a series of (rough) proxies which can be used to corroborate the general tenets of our hypothesis regarding the relationship between increasing social complexity and the emergence of polycentric political order. Even though more research is needed, this analysis sets the scene for an exciting new direction of historical and political studies.

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